

Stability in heterodyne phase-locking

P_a - power of active laser
 P_s - Power of slave laser
 (corrected to quantum efficiency of PD)

Photodetector Current:

$$I = \frac{e}{h\nu} (P_a + P_s) + 2\sqrt{P_a P_s} \cdot \cos(\Omega t + \varphi) + \delta I(t) ; \delta I(t) - \text{shot noise.}$$

Estimation of φ :

$$\tilde{\varphi} \approx \text{tg } \tilde{\varphi} = \frac{I_1^{\uparrow}}{I_2^{\uparrow}} = \frac{I_{10}^{\uparrow} + \delta I_1^{\uparrow}}{I_{20}^{\uparrow} + \delta I_2^{\uparrow}} \approx \frac{I_{10}^{\uparrow}}{I_{20}^{\uparrow}} + \frac{\delta I_1^{\uparrow}}{I_{20}^{\uparrow}}$$

More accurately! Measuring $\tilde{\varphi}$ over τ , we can calculate

$$\langle \tilde{\varphi}(t) \rangle_{\tau} \approx \frac{I_{10}^{\uparrow}}{I_{20}^{\uparrow}} + \frac{1}{I_{20}^{\uparrow} \tau} \int_{t-\tau/2}^{t+\tau/2} \delta I_1^{\uparrow}(t') dt'$$

Allan variance

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{\varphi}^2(\tau) &= \frac{1}{2} \left\langle \left(\int_t^{t+\tau} \frac{\delta I_1^{\uparrow}(t') dt'}{I_{20}^{\uparrow} \tau} - \int_{t-\tau}^t \frac{\delta I_1^{\uparrow}(t') dt'}{I_{20}^{\uparrow} \tau} \right)^2 \right\rangle = \\ &= \frac{1}{I_{20}^{\uparrow 2}} \frac{1}{2\tau^2} \left\langle \left(\int_t^{t+\tau} \delta I_1^{\uparrow}(t') dt' - \int_{t-\tau}^t \delta I_1^{\uparrow}(t') dt' \right)^2 \right\rangle \\ &\quad \underbrace{\hspace{10em}}_{\sigma_{I_1^{\uparrow}}^2(\tau)} \end{aligned}$$

to calculate $\sigma_{I^\uparrow}^2(\tau)$ we consider first power spectral density $S_{I^\uparrow}(f)$

$$S_{I^\uparrow}(f) = 2 \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \langle I^\uparrow(t) I^\uparrow(t+\tau) \rangle e^{2\pi i f \tau} d\tau$$

we should calculate $\langle I^\uparrow(t) I^\uparrow(t+\tau) \rangle$:

for the sake of simplicity, we can suppose that $I^\uparrow$ is limited in time, then we can perform Fourier transform:

$$\delta I^\uparrow(t) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \delta I^\uparrow(f) e^{2\pi i f t} df = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} F(f) e^{2\pi i f t} \delta I^\downarrow(f) df \quad \text{filter}$$

ideal filter: $F(f) = \begin{cases} 1, & |f| < f_c \\ 0, & |f| > f_c \end{cases}$

$$\textcircled{=} \int_{-f_c}^{f_c} \delta I^\downarrow(f) df e^{2\pi i f t} = \int_{-f_c}^{f_c} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \delta I^\downarrow(t') d \cdot e^{2\pi i f(t-t')} dt' df$$

$$\langle \delta I^\uparrow(t) \delta I^\uparrow(t') \rangle = \iint_{-f_c}^{f_c} \langle \delta I^\downarrow(f) \delta I^\downarrow(f') \rangle e^{2\pi i(f t + f' t')} df \cdot df'$$

$$\langle \delta I^\downarrow(f) \delta I^\downarrow(f') \rangle = \iint_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-2\pi i(f t + f' t')} \langle \delta I^\downarrow(t) \delta I^\downarrow(t') \rangle dt dt'$$

$$\delta I^\downarrow = \delta I \cdot \sin(\Omega t) \quad \delta I - \text{shot noise!}$$

$$\langle \delta I^\downarrow(t) \cdot \delta I^\downarrow(t') \rangle = \langle \sin(\Omega t) \sin(\Omega t') \rangle \langle \delta I(t) \delta I(t') \rangle = \frac{1}{2} \langle \delta I(t) \delta I(t') \rangle$$

$$\langle \delta I(t) \delta I(t') \rangle = \frac{e^2 P_s}{h \omega} \delta(t-t')$$

indeed, $\int_0^{\tau} \int_0^{\tau} \langle \delta I(t) \delta I(t') \rangle dt' dt = \frac{e^2 P_s}{h \omega} \tau$

$$\langle (\delta I(\tau))^2 \rangle = e^2 \frac{P_s \tau}{h \omega}$$

Poissonian statistics

Then $\langle \delta I^\downarrow(t) \cdot \delta I^\downarrow(t') \rangle = \frac{e^2 P_s}{2 h \omega} \delta(t-t')$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \langle \delta I^{\downarrow}(f) \delta I^{\downarrow}(f') \rangle &= \iint_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-2\pi i(f t + f' t')} \langle \delta I^{\downarrow}(t) \delta I^{\downarrow}(t') \rangle dt dt' = \\
 &= \frac{e^2 P_s}{2\pi\omega} \iint_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-2\pi i(f t + f' t')} \delta(t - t') dt dt' = \frac{e^2 P_s}{2\pi\omega} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-2\pi i(f + f')t} dt = \\
 &= \frac{e^2 P_s}{2\pi\omega} \delta(f + f')
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \langle \delta I^{\uparrow}(f) \delta I^{\uparrow}(f') \rangle &= \iint_{-f_c}^{f_c} \langle \delta I^{\downarrow}(f) \delta I^{\downarrow}(f') \rangle e^{2\pi i(f t + f' t')} df df' = \\
 &= \frac{e^2 P_s}{2\pi\omega} \int_{-f_c}^{f_c} e^{2\pi i f(t-t')} df = \frac{P_s e^2}{2\pi\omega} \frac{e^{2\pi i f_c(t-t')} - e^{-2\pi i f_c(t-t')}}{2\pi i(t-t')}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\langle \delta I^{\uparrow}(f) \delta I^{\uparrow}(f') \rangle = \frac{P_s e^2}{2\pi\omega} \frac{e^{2\pi i f_c(t-t')} - e^{-2\pi i f_c(t-t')}}{2\pi i(t-t')}$$

Spectral power density of fluctuations of $I^{\uparrow}$

$$S_{I^{\uparrow}}(f) = 2 \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \langle I^{\uparrow}(t) I^{\uparrow}(t+\tau) \rangle e^{2\pi i f \tau} d\tau$$

$$= \frac{P_s e^2}{\pi\omega} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{e^{2\pi i f_c \tau} - e^{-2\pi i f_c \tau}}{2\pi i \tau} e^{2\pi i f \tau} d\tau \quad (\ominus)$$

$$\text{v.p.} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{e^{i a \tau}}{i \tau} d\tau = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sin a \tau}{\tau} d\tau = \pi \cdot \text{sign}(a)$$

$$(\ominus) \frac{P_s e^2}{\pi\omega} \frac{1}{2} (\text{sign}(f_c + f) - \text{sign}(f - f_c)) = \frac{P_s e^2}{\pi\omega} \cdot \begin{cases} 1, & |f| < f_c \\ 0, & |f| > f_c \end{cases}$$

$$\sigma_{\varphi}^2(\tau) = \frac{1}{I_{20}^{\tau 2}} G_{I^{\tau}}^2(\tau) ; \quad I_{20}^{\tau 2} = 2 P_a P_s \cos \varphi \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{e^2}{(t\omega)^2} \stackrel{\varphi \ll 1}{=} \frac{P_a P_s e^2}{(t\omega)^2}$$

$$\Rightarrow S_{\varphi}(f) = \frac{1}{I_{20}^{\tau 2}} S_{I^{\tau}}(f) = \frac{(t\omega)^2}{P_a P_s e^2} \cdot \begin{cases} 1, |f| < f_c \\ 0, |f| > f_c \end{cases} = \frac{t\omega}{P_a} \cdot \begin{cases} 1, |f| < f_c \\ 0, |f| > f_c \end{cases}$$

$$S_{\varphi}(f) = \frac{t\omega}{P_a} \cdot \begin{cases} 1, |f| < f_c \\ 0, |f| > f_c \end{cases} \Rightarrow S_y(f) = S_{\varphi}(f) \cdot \frac{f^2}{(\omega/2\pi)^2}$$

$$y = \frac{\dot{\varphi}}{\omega}$$

$$S_y(f) = \frac{4\pi^2 f^2}{\omega^2} \frac{t\omega}{P_a} \cdot \begin{cases} 1, |f| < f_c \\ 0, |f| > f_c \end{cases}$$

To calculate Allan variance of y , we do

$$G_y^2(\tau) = 2 \int_0^{\infty} S_y(f) \frac{\sin^4(\pi f \tau)}{(\pi f \tau)^2} df$$

see, for ex., F. Riehle,
"Frequency standards"

$$G_y^2(\tau) = 2 \int_0^{f_c} \frac{4\pi^2 f^2}{\omega^2} \frac{t\omega}{P_a} \frac{\sin^4(\pi f \tau)}{(\pi f \tau)^2} df = \frac{8t}{\omega P_a \tau^2} \int_0^{f_c} \sin^4(\pi f \tau) df \stackrel{f_c \tau \gg 1}{\approx} \frac{8t f_c}{\omega P_a \tau^2} \cdot \frac{3}{8} = \frac{3t f_c}{\omega P_a \tau^2}$$

$$G_y(\tau) = \frac{1}{\tau} \sqrt{\frac{3t f_c}{\omega P_a}}$$

$$\sin^4 \alpha = (\sin^2 \alpha)^2 = \left(\frac{1 - \cos 2\alpha}{2} \right)^2 = \frac{1}{4} (1 - 2 \cos 2\alpha + \cos^2 2\alpha)$$